

CORRUPT PROBLEMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE TEACHING SYSTEM OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN TODAY

¹Khimmataliyev D.O, ²Eshbekova G.Kh.

¹Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

²Tashkent region Chirchik State Pedagogical University Master's student in the field of management of educational institutions

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7566300>

Abstract. *If we look at the reasons of not flourishing in school system, there is a bitter conclusion about hindering to accomplish teachers' professional duties who really adore their jobs and feel their duties or responsibilities for the future of the country. In the past, de jury, teachers' rights and beliefs were not defended. That's to say, teachers were forced different kind of jobs which were not on their duties. They were involved in various voluntary works that directly reduced their status in the society. Thus, many problems had been emerged in this sector. These snags definitely could not be solved at once, however, it needs much effort and time in the long run.*

Keywords: *corrupt, combat corruption, education, unethical behavior, favoritism, curriculum, governance, schools mechanism, reforms, transparency, private tutoring, teaching methods, mainstream teachers, scepticism.*

Considering the public education sector as a most important and the largest sector in all countries, it requires reforms in the curriculum as well as in governance. Especially in the poor or developing societies the results show enough low points in this sector. "The education sector consumes around 20percent and 30 percent of the total budget, the employers by far the highest percentage of educated human recourses (administrates, inspectors, teachers, and professors), and concerns between 20 percent and 25 percent of the population (pupils and students, parents and other stakeholders)."("Corrupt schools, corrupt universities: What can be done? "UNESCO Publishing 2007 page23).Therefore, societies must really rethink their educational system and curriculums which aids to develop in every sphere of these countries, particularly developing economies.

As well, in Uzbekistan the authorities endeavoring to eliminate problematic issues ,which occur in its educational system, force everyone to participate and contribute to the educational process in many ways. Much regulations in governance of schools , introducing some new legislations to prevent ethical norms in schools have been to the point where the staff of teachers are being skeptical about the educational reforms as well as of the government's claims. We can consider this as a first major reason for becoming neglected area by the government during decades. Meanwhile, having low efficacy and quality of learning in education sector, or high unemployment rates among graduates not only in our country but the stags seem to have in other societies also.

A mass of problems have piled due to negligence for several decades in public schools in Uzbekistan. Even up to these days fundamental or pressing problems in education sector have not covered in news, current affairs programs or specialized programs for educational affairs

throughout Uzbekistan. Hence, corruption has gradually rooted and educational institutions, schools have become one of the corrupt areas among others. But now education has become on top agenda on news in the mass media.

Paying much attention on this sector the president of Uzbekistan has been striving for greater achievements and goals. Gained lost status among society teachers are also inspired by him. Every citizen in the country has green light to be educated now. On article 5 in the “Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education” tells that every citizen have access to be educated. Despite the attempts, educational processes in public schools face with difficulties which can be described as unethical behaviorism, unacceptable etiquette.

If we look at the reasons of not flourishing in school system, there is a bitter conclusion about hindering to accomplish teachers’ professional duties who really adore their jobs and feel their duties or responsibilities for the future of the country. In the past, de jury, teachers’ rights and beliefs were not defended. That’s to say, teachers were forced different kind of jobs which were not on their duties. They were involved in various voluntary works that directly reduced their status in the society. Thus, many problems had been emerged in this sector. These snags definitely could not be solved at once, however, it needs much effort and time in the long run.

A recent survey conducted by a professor Kobilov Sharif and his team public schools were the third largest area where 24,9 percent citizens feel that corruption is widespread in this sector, yet 48,4 percent respondents consider that corruption occurs in some schools not in all. Whereas 19,7 percent people think corruption in schools is unavailable and 7,0 percent respondents who answered the question whether corruption exists in school or not gave vague ideas about it. These facts show that the schools mechanism should be learnt properly.

Good, proper education and deep knowledge leads to prosperity of the country, therefore why not identify the causes for pervading corruption in schools. Through identifying them it can be seen further pro-developments all different branches across the country. Regarding vulnerability to pervasive corruption in schools is insufficient salaries for teachers. This pushes them to give extra lessons to pupils after school which aims financial gain and burden to parents as well. Still, private tutoring has positive purposes when public schools support students who have lower grades with the free use of state facilities in order to improve their level:

- it enhances student’s studying;
- it helps not to waste time after school;
- it is great chance to have supplementary earning for teachers;
- it provides a good opportunity for both for children who cannot achieve sufficient marks and for their parents as remedy courses;
- it helps strengthen students’ confidence and enables them to compete with their peers honestly and others.

Nevertheless, additional private tutoring has already become a major business industry that is draining parents’ income and consuming pupils’ time. Adversely, mainstream education is affected by it as a source of corruption.”A study on the Republic of Korea shows that expenditure on private tutoring by the richest 10% of the surveyed population is 12 times as high as that spent by the poorest 10%. Unlike most shadows, private tutoring is not just a passive entity but may negatively affect even the body which it imitates.”(Source: Bray 2003;21.) The trend of educating schoolchildren in private tutoring has also accelerated in Uzbekistan which affects negatively the behavior of teachers, students, and parents. Furthermore, private tutoring grows unfavorable

attitude towards mainstream education and corrupt practices. Usually, some mainstream teachers teach only the part of the topics which is planned to be taught on the syllabus. Thus, being aware or not these secondary school teachers force their own students to attend their extra lessons in order to pass academic exams.

Another cause for behaving corruptly is that some school teachers deliberately make the exam questions difficult or facing students with any competitions for not getting high marks or exerting pressure on their parents to send them their unofficial working hours of teaching. This dishonest unethical behavior of teachers creates unequal environment among students in the classroom and develop skepticism to the educational system. The outcome would be definitely penalization students differently.

To state the next cause about assisting to develop private tutoring is lack of experienced teachers who fully understand and know the subjects to be taught. For that reason private tutors may gain more prestige over secondary school teachers, and students mostly rely on their tutors because of tight relationship between them.

Absenteeism of teachers in public schools for no reasons at all sometimes making their excuses is the other issue which pushes students to take extra lessons.

All in all, if teachers do not lead classes professionally and students cannot satisfy with the lessons, this ends up to the advantage of private tutoring. Creating favorable atmosphere for teachers may prevent corruption in education.

Mentally fatigued private tutors could undermine the state educational system. Because being overloaded with their own work teachers who also work at state schools have less preference to conduct professional and interesting classes under their responsibility. In a consequence, instead promote integrity, transparency they encourage favoritism and corrupt behavior showing disrespect to the system and ethical norms.

Private tutoring has negative impact on the state school system and it aids to develop dishonest, immoral behavior among youth. On the other hand, it is not bad when tutoring provides via transparent system. So as to acquire good governance, school managers should make great efforts to reach and maintain teachers' moral obligations. This is teachers who are responsible for strengthening students' moral values and bonds between students. To combat corruption, there is a need to reform in school management and curriculum emphasizing teachers, students, and parental involvement. Moreover, private tutoring cannot be banned directly for many reasons i.e. before giving a good salary increase, recruiting psyched-up professional teachers and protecting teachers' interests. Further recommendations would help combat corruption in public schools:

- to extend the teaching hours at schools;
- and collaboration of two teachers: the usual teacher and an assistant teacher working together in one class where the amount of students is over 30 to reach the obedience to class rules;
- forcing students to work together to do project presentations maintaining them to spend more time in school libraries;
- To avoid traditional teaching methods;
- in order to fairly assessing students' knowledge computerized online testing should be held.

When these all are managed properly, without any doubt teachers can contribute good changes towards better participation on building transparent as well as anti-corruption educational system.

REFERENCES

1. Bray, M. 1999. "The shadow education system: private tutoring and its implications for planners (Fundamentals of Educational Planning No.61)". Paris: IIEP-UNESCO
2. J. Hallak, M. Poisson 2007. "Corrupt schools, corrupt universities: What can be done?" UNESCO Publishing
3. Shavkat Mirziyoyev "Development strategy of new Uzbekistan" Uzbekistan, Tashkent-2022
4. Monica Kirya "Education sector corruption: How to assess it and ways to address it" CM Michelsen
5. Institute U4 issue 2019 B.A. Aliyev, A. Muxtarov "Uzbekistan's anti-corruption strategy" Innovative development publishing house-2021
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" lex.uz 2022